

CONTENTS

Sr. No.	Author	Title	Page Numbers	Full Text
01	Krishanu Adhikari	Rohinton Mistry's Such A Long Journey: An Immigrant's Rendition of Cultural Amnesia, Nationalism and Politics of Dislocation	01 -12	PDF
02	Dr. Arshad Ahmad	Maya as an Existential Character in Anita Desai's Cry, the Peacock	13-17	PDF
03	Akshay Kumar	Women as Victims of Power in Vijay Tendulkar's Kamala	18-26	PDF
04	Archana Bagga	Narrating the Nation and Culture: A Study of Shashi Deshpande's 3 Novels	27-41	PDF
05	Barkha, Anshika	Existential Predicament in Arun Joshi's Novels	42-47	PDF
06	Dr. A.K. Chaturvedi	Paulo Coelho's The Pilgrimage: A Unique Search for the Meaningful	48-55	PDF

Sr. No.	Author	Title	Page Numbers	Full Text
07	Deepshikha Kumari	Seattle's 'Simple Philosophy': A Plea of an Environmentalist	56-59	PDF
08	Dr. Dashrath Gatt	Feministic Concerns through Fleshy Designs: A Revisit to Saadat Hasan Manto's Short Stories	60-68	PDF
09	Bhaskar Jyoti Gogoi	Historical Re-Interpretations: Writing/Re-Writing of Ethnography and Historiography	69-74	PDF
10	Seyed Javad Habibi	Imagosynthesis: Poetic Photosynthesis in Wordsworth's "Resolution and Independence"	75-84	PDF
11	Jayashree Hazarika	Globalization in the Works of Vikram Seth	85-89	PDF
12	Dr. Indrani Singh Rai	A Stream Within: Discourse of a Subaltern in Mahasweta Devi's Outcast: Four Stories	90-93	PDF
13	Sahidul Islam & Masuda Alfaruque	Kureishi's "The Buddha of Suburbia": Post-Imperial Vacuity and Quest for Identity	94-98	PDF
14	Soumen Jana	The Problematics of 'Dalit space' in Sarat Chandra Chattopadhyay's "Mahesh" and Mahasweta Devi's "Shikar"	99-105	PDF
15	Ravinder Kaur	George Eliot's The Mill on the Floss: The Construction of Gender Roles	106-112	PDF
16	Najme Khademi & Pyeaaam Abbasi	Jane Eyre: Serving the Empire	113-130	PDF
17	Rajender Kumar	Amorous Love in the Novels of Earnest Hemingway: A Romantic Study of A Farewell to Arms	131-135	PDF
18	Lalit Kumar	Ideology of the Photographs: Thinking with Sontag and Butler	136-141	PDF
19	Dr. Neelam Mor	Class-Consciousness and Conjugal Relations in John Osborne's Look Back in Anger (1957)	142-147	PDF
20	Mudasir Ahmad Shah	Tughlaq: History Revisited	148-157	PDF
21	Kritika Nanda	Niccolo Machiavelli's The Prince: An Overview	158-161	PDF

Sr. No.	Author	Title	Page Numbers	Full Text
22	Nilesh Prakash Bhillade	To Speak About the Unspeakable: Marginalized Position of Class, Community and Gender	162-168	PDF
23	Omila Thounaojam	Slavery and Racism in Toni Morrison's A Mercy	169-175	PDF
24	Padumi Singha	Surfacing: The Recovery of a Displaced Identity	176-183	PDF
25	Prachand Narayan Piraji	Rewriting Histories - A Struggle for 'Self Identity' as a Human Being: Reading of Untouchable Spring and Outcaste: A Memoir	184-189	PDF
26	Preeti Puri	Diasporic Consciousness: A Comparative Study of Jhumpa Lahiri's The Namesake and Kiran Desai's The Inheritance of Loss	190-194	PDF
27	M. David Raju	Black Humour and Ennui in Upamanyu Chatterjee's English, August: An Indian Story	195-204	PDF
28	Dr. Ram Krishna Thakur	Delineation of English Language Teaching Syllabi and Its Implications	205-214	PDF
29	Charanpreet Randhawa	Diasporic Discourse in Rohinton Mistry's Such a Long Journey	215-225	PDF
30	Dr. Romika Batra Sukhija	Postmodern Feminist Reverberations in Manju Kapur's Home	226-235	PDF
31	Dr. Roopesh Chaturvedi & Dr. Anoop Tiwari	The Partition of Indian Subcontinent: Crisis of Identity and Uprooted Nationalities Resulting in Double Disaster for Pakistan	236-240	PDF
32	Rukhsana Saifee & Dr. Mukta Sharma	Chitra Bannerjee Divakaruni's Literature on the Dilemma of Women Living in Alien Culture	241-243	PDF
33	Samya Achiri	Private Life Versus Political Clutches in Nadine Gordimer's Burger's Daughter	244-248	PDF
34	Dr. Sanchita Choudhury & Sagarika Dash	Yajnaseni: A Synonym of Indian Woman	249-256	PDF
35	Sara Soleimani Karbalaei	An Unofficial Rose and Murdochian Existentialist Style	257-270	PDF

Sr. No.	Author	Title	Page Numbers	Full Text
36	Sathyapriya.K	Ethnic Belief in Ngugi Wa Thiong'o's Novels	271-278	PDF
37	Dr. P. Satyanarayana	Alice Munro: A Master of Canadian Short Story	279-286	PDF
38	Dr. Priti Bala Sharma	Teaching Communication Skills in English through Translation: An Effective Methodology for the Beginners (Engineering Students) from Rural Background	287-293	PDF
39	Kanwarpal Singh	Amitav Ghosh's Vision of Man-Woman Relationship in The Hungry Tide	294-299	PDF
40	Dr. Siva Nagaiah Bolleddu	A Dissent Study on Gender Studies in India	300-303	PDF
41	Dr. Somveer	Non-Marital Sex in John Osborne's Inadmissible Evidence and Time Present	304-310	PDF
42	Sumbul	Chinua Achebe's Things Fall Apart: Exploring the Ibo Culture and the Aspect of Gender Bias	311-314	PDF
43	Tarun D. Rawal	William Butler Yeats and India: A Study in Reception of Literary and Philosophical Influences	315-319	PDF
44	Dr. Mangala Tomar	Mythology in Arun Joshi's Novel	320-325	PDF
45	Vaseemahmed G. Qureshi	Exploring Young-ness and Uncle-ness of Younguncle in Vandana Singh's Literary Creation Younguncle Comes to Town	326-328	PDF
46	Veena Sindhu	The White Tiger: Challenges of Urbanization	329-335	PDF
47	Dr. (Mrs).N.Velmani	Ethnicity in the Novels of Vikram Seth	336-340	PDF
48	Vinod Kumar	Sunil Khilnani's Idea of India: An Ideological Critique on his Book The Idea of India (1997)	341-354	PDF
FICTION				
49	Edgar Rider	Bring Back Malone	355-366	PDF
50	Ilyas Babar Awan	The Suicide Bomber	367-371	PDF

Sr. No.	Author	Title	Page Numbers	Full Text
51	John Gorman	The TV Freak	372-378	PDF
52	Rama Shivakumar	The Raaga Inside	379-388	PDF
53	Tawqeer Nasir Tak	Chor...the word still echoes!	389-391	PDF
POETRY				
54	Annu Yadav	Let me be alone...	392-393	PDF
55	Anthony Villett	When You in Days No Longer Smile	394	PDF
56	Dr. Anuradha Kherdekar	The Line	395	PDF
57	Betsy Hulick	Absence Cannot Be Imagined, Only Felt	396	PDF
58	Mamud Hassan	Is This A Democracy?	397	PDF
59	Parneet Jaggi	Not an Inch	398	PDF
60	Nivedita Yohana	Born Into This Carnival of Rust	399	PDF
61	Steven Sher	Joining Hands	400	PDF
62	Bupinder Singh	A Rape Victim's Cry	401	PDF
63	Swanti Sharma	Come Unburden Your Mind	402	PDF
BOOK REVIEW				
64	Dr. I.Venkateswarlu	So Many Freedoms by Karanam Rao	403-404	PDF
65	Samarendra Mohapatra	The Rage in Albion by Cecelia Peters	405-407	PDF
INTERVIEW				
66	Elizabeth Waterhouse	An Interview with Poet Sonnet Mondal	408-410	PDF